

The luminous flux and the case of several charts

Harald Schröer

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The parametrization with one chart is not possible for all sources and receivers. Because of this we treat the parametrization with several charts.

We need a theorem about the integral over manifolds with several charts.

theorem 1: see Forster [1] "Analysis 3" §14 p.138,139

Let be M a k -dimensional submanifold

$$f : M \rightarrow R \quad \varphi_j : T_j \rightarrow V_j \subset M \quad M \subset R^n$$

Let be $\varphi_1, \dots, \varphi_m$ charts with $\bigcup_{j=1}^m V_j = M$

Then it is valid: Dann gilt:

$$\int_M f(x) dS(x) = \sum_{j=1}^m \int_{V_j} \alpha_j(x) \cdot f(x) dS(x)$$

$$:= \sum_{j=1}^m \int_{T_j} \alpha_j(\varphi_j(t)) \cdot f(\varphi_j(t)) \cdot \sqrt{g_j(t)} d^k t$$

$$t \in T_j \subset R^k \quad x \in V_j \subset M$$

$g_j(t)$ is the Gram determinant of φ_j .

$$g_j(t) = \det G_j \quad G_j = (D\varphi_j)^T \cdot D\varphi_j$$

see Forster [1] "Analysis 3" §14 p.136-139 and §3 p.29

$D\varphi_j$ = Jacobi-matrix of φ_j with t

A^T is the transpose matrix of A .

α_j is a **partition of unity**, that has the following properties see Forster [1] "Analysis 3" §14 p.139:

- i) $0 \leq \alpha_j \leq 1 \quad \alpha_j(M \setminus V_j) = 0$
- ii) $\sum_{j=1}^m \alpha_j(x) = 1 \quad \text{for all } x \in M$

iii) $t \rightarrow \alpha_j(\varphi_j(t))$ must be local integrable on T_j see Forster [1] "Analysis 3" §9 p.87.

In Forster [1] "Analysis 3" §14 p.139 it is shown that the integral's definition is independent from the cover of M and the partition of unity. The exact definitions of immersions and charts are in Forster [1] "Analysis 3" §14 p.132,134.

theorem 2:

$$\varphi_j : U_j \rightarrow V_j \quad f : V \rightarrow R \quad U_j, V \subset R^n$$

$$y \in U_j \quad x \in V \quad \bigcup_{j=1}^m V_j = V$$

$$\begin{aligned} \int_V f(x) d^n x &= \sum_{j=1}^m \int_{V_j} f(x) d^n x \\ &= \sum_{j=1}^m \int_{U_j} f(\varphi_j(y)) \cdot |\det D\varphi_j(y)| d^n y \end{aligned}$$

is the transformation formula see Forster [1] "Analysis 3" §13 theorem 2 p.120. φ_j must be bijective for $j \in 1 \dots m$. $\varphi_j, \varphi_j^{-1}$ must be continuous differentiable for $j \in 1 \dots m$. $U_1, \dots, U_m, V_1, \dots, V_m$ are open sets.

We have a light source with the volume $V(t)$ [t = time] and a receiver with the surface $A(t)$.

$$V(t) \cap A(t) = \emptyset$$

The source and the receiver shall be in medium, for example: pure air with constant density. That means the absorption coefficient m is constant. The medium is in the whole room. The problem is to get the luminous flux that is received by $A(t)$. $B(t)$ shall be the surface of the light source.

$w(\vec{b}, t)$ = surface luminous intensity density of the light source $\vec{b} \in B(t)$

$$B(t) = \bigcup_{j=1}^m B_j(t)$$

$$B_j(t) = \vec{e}_j(\vec{y}, t) \quad j \in 1 \dots m$$

The $\vec{e}_j$ are the **charts**(parametrizations) for every $t \in R$.

$$\vec{e}_j : U_j \times R \longrightarrow B_j(t) \quad \vec{y} \in U_j \subset R^2$$

If I is the luminous intensity of the source, then we have:

$$I(t) = \int_{B(t)} w(\vec{b}, t) d\vec{b} = \sum_{j=1}^m \int_{B_j(t)} w(\vec{b}, t) d\vec{b} \quad (1)$$

with theorem 1:

$$I(t) = \sum_{j=1}^m \int_{U_j} \alpha_j(\vec{e}_j(\vec{y}, t)) \cdot w(\vec{e}_j(\vec{y}, t), t) \cdot \sqrt{g_j(\vec{y})} d\vec{y}$$

$\alpha_j \quad j \in 1 \dots m$ is a partition of unity.

$$\text{with } g_j(\vec{y}) = \det G_j \quad G_j = (D\vec{e}_j)^T \cdot D\vec{e}_j$$

$$D\vec{e}_j := D\vec{e}_j(\vec{y})$$

$g_j(\vec{y})$ is the Gram determinant of $\vec{e}_j$.

Now we calculate the illumination $\vec{E}$:

We need:

$e(\dots)$ = absorption factor

m = absorption coefficient $m = \text{const.}$

$$e(\vec{a}, \vec{x}) = e^{-m \cdot |\vec{a} - \vec{x}|} \quad \vec{a}, \vec{x} \in R^3$$

Then we obtain the illumination:

$$\begin{aligned} \vec{E}(\vec{a}, t) &= \int_{B(t)} w(\vec{b}, t) \cdot e(\vec{a}, \vec{b}) \cdot \frac{\vec{a} - \vec{b}}{|\vec{a} - \vec{b}|^3} d\vec{b} \\ &= \sum_{j=1}^m \int_{B_j(t)} w(\vec{b}, t) \cdot e(\vec{a}, \vec{b}) \cdot \frac{\vec{a} - \vec{b}}{|\vec{a} - \vec{b}|^3} d\vec{b} \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

$$\begin{aligned} B_j(t) &= \vec{e}_j(\vec{y}, t) & \vec{e}_j : U_j \times R &\longrightarrow B_j(t) \\ j \in 1 \dots m & & \vec{y} \in U_j \subset R^2 & \end{aligned}$$

see theorem 1:

$$\vec{E}(\vec{a}, t) = \sum_{j=1}^m \int_{U_j} \alpha_j(\vec{e}_j(\vec{y}, t)) \cdot w(\vec{e}_j(\vec{y}, t), t) \cdot e(\vec{a}, \vec{e}_j(\vec{y}, t)) \cdot \frac{\vec{a} - \vec{e}_j(\vec{y}, t)}{|\vec{a} - \vec{e}_j(\vec{y}, t)|^3} \cdot \sqrt{g_j(\vec{y})} d\vec{y} \quad (3)$$

α_j = partition of unity $\vec{y} \in U_j \subset R^2$

$$g_j(\vec{y}) = \det [(D\vec{e}_j)^T \cdot D\vec{e}_j]$$

$$D\vec{e}_j := D\vec{e}_j(\vec{y})$$

On this way, we get an 2-dimensional integral. At (3) we can possibly do a further transformation with theorem 2 to simplify.

In vacuum is:
 $m = 0 \Rightarrow e(\vec{a}, \vec{b}) = 1$

$\vec{n}_j$ is the exterior normal unit vector of $B_j(t)$. $j \in 1 \dots m$

Then we can see, that $\angle(\vec{n}_j, (\vec{a} - \vec{b})) \leq 90^\circ$ is a necessary but not sufficient condition to attain the point $\vec{a}$ (see the both figures).

light source

light source

At (2) and (3) we need possibly only an integration over a subset of $B_j(t)$ respectively U_j for $j \in 1 \dots m$.

calculation of $\vec{n}_j(\vec{y})$:

$$B_j(t) = \vec{c}_j(\vec{y}, t) \quad \vec{y} \in U_j \subset R^2 \quad \vec{y} = (y_1, y_2)$$

tangent vectors at $\vec{c}_j : U_j \times R \rightarrow B_j(t)$ see Forster [1] "Analysis 3" §15 theorem 1 p.148 are $\frac{\partial}{\partial y_1} \vec{c}_j(\vec{y}, t)$ and $\frac{\partial}{\partial y_2} \vec{c}_j(\vec{y}, t)$.

exterior normal unit vector:

$$\pm n_j(\vec{y}) = \frac{\frac{\partial}{\partial y_1} \vec{c}_j(\vec{y}, t) \times \frac{\partial}{\partial y_2} \vec{c}_j(\vec{y}, t)}{\left| \frac{\partial}{\partial y_1} \vec{c}_j(\vec{y}, t) \times \frac{\partial}{\partial y_2} \vec{c}_j(\vec{y}, t) \right|} \quad (4)$$

restrictive condition:

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha(t) = \angle(\vec{n}_j, \vec{a} - \vec{b}) \leq 90^\circ & \Rightarrow \cos \alpha(t) \geq 0 \\ \Rightarrow \frac{\vec{n}_j(\vec{y}) \cdot (\vec{a} - \vec{b})}{|\vec{n}_j(\vec{y})| \cdot |\vec{a} - \vec{b}|} = \cos \alpha(t) \geq 0 & \quad (5) \end{aligned}$$

or

$$\vec{n}_j(\vec{y}) \cdot (\vec{a} - \vec{b}) \geq 0 \quad (6)$$

Now we occupy with the luminous flux through the surface $A(t)$.

$$A(t) = \bigcup_{j=1}^m A_j(t)$$

$$\vec{c}_j : V_j \times R \rightarrow A(t) \quad \vec{c}_j(\vec{p}, t) = A(t) \quad \vec{p} \in V_j \subset R^2$$

The $\vec{c}_j$ are the charts.

$\vec{n}_j$ = exterior normal unit vector of $\vec{c}_j$ respectively $A_j(t)$

It follows for the luminous flux through the receiver A :

$$\Phi(t) = \left| \sum_{j=1}^m \int_{A_j(t)} \vec{E}(\vec{a}, t) \cdot \vec{n}_j(\vec{a}, t) d\vec{a} \right| \quad (7)$$

with theorem 1:

$$\Phi(t) = \left| \sum_{j=1}^m \int_{V_j} \alpha_j(\vec{c}_j(\vec{p}, t)) \cdot \vec{E}(\vec{c}_j(\vec{p}, t), t) \cdot \vec{n}_j(\vec{p}) \cdot \sqrt{g_j(\vec{p})} d\vec{p} \right| \quad (8)$$

$\alpha_j =$ partition of unity

$$g_j(\vec{p}) := \det [(D\vec{c}_j)^T \cdot D\vec{c}_j] \quad (\text{Gram determinant})$$

$$D\vec{c}_j = D\vec{c}_j(\vec{p})$$

The luminous flux is reduced to an 2-dimensional integral. At (8) we can possibly do a further transformation with theorem 2 to simplify.

At the figure we can see the following: On complicated receivers we can possibly integrate only over a subset of $A(t)$. A necessary but not a sufficient condition to attain $\vec{a}$:

$$\beta(t) = \angle(\vec{E}(\vec{a}), \vec{n}_j) \geq 90^\circ$$

$$\Rightarrow \frac{\vec{n}_j(\vec{a}) \cdot \vec{E}(\vec{a})}{|\vec{n}_j(\vec{a})| \cdot |\vec{E}(\vec{a})|} = \cos \beta(t) \leq 0 \quad (9)$$

$$\Rightarrow \vec{n}_j(\vec{a}) \cdot \vec{E}(\vec{a}) \leq 0 \quad (10)$$

$$\vec{c}_j : V_j \times R \longrightarrow A_j(t) \quad \vec{c}_j(\vec{p}, t) = A_j(t) \quad \vec{p} = (p_1, p_2) \in V_j \subset R^2$$

is the chart respectively the parametrization of $A_j(t)$.

$\frac{\partial}{\partial p_1} \vec{c}_j(\vec{p}, t)$ and $\frac{\partial}{\partial p_2} \vec{c}_j(\vec{p}, t)$ are tangent vectors at $\vec{c}_j : V_j \times R \longrightarrow A_j(t)$ see Forster [1] "Analysis 3" §15 theorem 1 p.148. We conclude for the exterior normal unit vector:

$$\pm \vec{n}_j(\vec{p}) = \frac{\frac{\partial}{\partial p_1} \vec{c}_j(\vec{p}, t) \times \frac{\partial}{\partial p_2} \vec{c}_j(\vec{p}, t)}{\left| \frac{\partial}{\partial p_1} \vec{c}_j(\vec{p}, t) \times \frac{\partial}{\partial p_2} \vec{c}_j(\vec{p}, t) \right|} \quad (11)$$

with (10) we obtain at last:

$$\vec{n}_j(\vec{p}) \cdot \vec{E}(\vec{c}_j(\vec{p}, t), t) \leq 0 \quad (12)$$

special case: the point source

$\vec{x}$ = the point source's position

The illumination can be presented as:

$$\vec{E}(a) = \frac{I(t) \cdot (\vec{a} - \vec{x})}{|\vec{a} - \vec{x}|^3} \cdot e(\vec{a}, \vec{x}) \quad I = \text{luminous intensity} \quad (13)$$

$$\vec{x} \neq \vec{a}$$

We obtain for the luminous flux through the surface $A(t)$:

$$\Phi = I \cdot \left| \sum_{j=1}^m \int_{A_j} \frac{(\vec{a} - \vec{x})}{|\vec{a} - \vec{x}|^3} \cdot e(\vec{a}, \vec{x}) \cdot \vec{n}_j(\vec{a}) \, da \right| \quad (14)$$

transformation with:

$$\vec{c}_j : V_j \times R \longrightarrow A_j(t) \quad \vec{c}_j(\vec{p}, t) = A_j(t) \quad \vec{p} \in V_j \subset R^2$$

$$\Phi = I \cdot \left| \sum_{j=1}^m \int_{V_j} \alpha_j(\vec{c}_j(\vec{p})) \frac{(\vec{c}_j(\vec{p}) - \vec{x})}{|\vec{c}_j(\vec{p}) - \vec{x}|^3} \cdot e(\vec{c}_j(\vec{p}), \vec{x}) \cdot \vec{n}_j(\vec{c}_j(\vec{p})) \cdot \sqrt{g_j(\vec{p})} \, d\vec{p} \right| \quad (15)$$

with

$$g_j(\vec{p}) = \det [(D\vec{c}_j(\vec{p}))^T \cdot D\vec{c}_j(\vec{p})]$$

Without I and without a medium we have a general formula for the solid angle.

References

- [1] Otto Forster "Analysis 3" 2.edition 1983 Vieweg Verlag Brunswick
- [2] Harald Schröer "Luminous Flux and Illumination" Wissenschaft & Technik Verlag Berlin 2001